

A Journey to the Magical World (Harry Potter and Hashimjon)

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Abstract. This article briefly explores the journeys of the main characters, Hashimjon from Khudoyberdi To'xtaboyev's «Sariq devni minib» and Harry from J.K. Rowling's «Harry Potter va afsonaviy tosh», into worlds of magic and adventure. It highlights the fantastical aspects of Harry's world and the adventurous experiences of Hashimjon.

Key words: Childhood, fantasy, destiny, adventure, virtual and real life, Harry Potter and Hashimjon, wizardry, plot, bestsellers..

Introduction: «Harry Potter va afsonaviy tosh» is the first book in the famous “Harry Potter” series by British author J.K. Rowling. The books center on young wizard Harry Potter and his friends, Ron Weasley and Hermione Granger, and their adventures at Hogwarts School of Witchcraft and Wizardry. «Sariq devni minib» by Khudoyberdi To'xtaboyev follows the adventures of Hashimjon, who, despite his youth, is determined to become an agronomist and embarks on explorations with a magical hat, portrayed with a humorous tone.

Main Body: *Harry Potter* and «Sariq devni minib» are celebrated works in both English and Uzbek children's literature and have gained worldwide acclaim as bestsellers. While *Harry Potter*, written by J.K. Rowling, takes place entirely in a magical, fantastical realm, To'xtaboyev's «Sariq devni minib» is a treasure of Uzbek children's literature that portrays a lighthearted and joyous look at childhood. The heroes in both books experience lives filled with adventure, though Harry's is grounded in fantasy, while Hashimjon's adventures are more realistic and relatable.

While Harry Potter is a young wizard, Hashimjon and his friends are ordinary kids who embark on more down-to-earth adventures based on realistic events. «*Harry Potter va afsonaviy tosh*» starts with Harry being left at the home of his aunt and uncle, the Dursleys, after the tragic death of his parents at the hands of dark forces. The story introduces Professor McGonagall, Dumbledore, and Hagrid as they bring Harry to his new home:

“People say,” continued Professor McGonagall in a solemn tone, “that last night Voldemort went to Godric's Hollow to kill the Potters. According to the rumors, Lily and James Potter... they perished. Dumbledore nodded sorrowfully. “Is it true?” Professor McGonagall choked up. “After all he's done... he couldn't kill a child? Is it possible that his powers could end in such a way? How could...” (gazing skyward), “Harry survive?”

“These are the people who live here?” Professor McGonagall exclaimed, gesturing towards 4 Privet Drive. “Dumbledore... you don't have the right. I watched them all day. They're the worst sort of people!”

Harry is thus left with the Dursleys, where he is met with neglect and even hostility, especially from his cousin, Dudley. Despite this, he eventually receives an invitation to Hogwarts, the school of wizardry, through letters that are almost taken from him by his aunt and uncle. Finally, with Hagrid's help, he gets to read one and learns the truth about his magical heritage and the fame of his parents in the wizarding world. Awed and overwhelmed, Harry realizes his life will never be the same.

“Who am I?” asked Harry, stunned. “You’re a wizard,” replied Hagrid, with a booming laugh as he settled on the couch. “And a mighty good one if you train for it. Now, go ahead, read this letter.”

With that, Harry’s magical journey at Hogwarts begins, and he forms deep friendships with Ron and Hermione, learning lessons about loyalty and friendship.

Riding the Yellow Giant, one of the first fantastic works in Uzbek children’s literature, captures the innocent, fun-filled experiences of childhood. The story begins with Hashimjon introducing himself:

“Allow me to introduce myself: my name is Hashim, but you can call me Hashimjon. My last name is Roziyev; my father is Rozi, the tractor driver. My mother works on a farm, milking cows. She even won a medal for her hard work last year.”

Hashimjon, unlike other children, is mischievous, slightly rebellious, yet immensely affectionate, especially towards his sisters. His playful personality and curious nature lead him on an exciting adventure. After being influenced by tales his grandmother told him, he embarks on a quest for a magical cap. Despite being locked out of his house for misbehavior, Hashimjon turns the situation to his advantage and heads to the village outskirts to search for his treasure.

“In the evening, after being forbidden from entering the house, I borrowed two loaves of bread from our neighbor and headed to an abandoned house. Every corner seemed haunted by ghosts and demons.”

Eventually, Hashimjon discovers the cap:

“I felt around in the corner... I found it, can you believe it? The soft, snowy-white cap!

“Hello, my cap!” I shouted.

“Hello, Hashimjon!” echoed a voice.”

With his newfound friend, Hashimjon begins an exciting journey, aspiring to become a skilled worker as he travels to faraway places.

Conclusion: Both *Harry Potter* and «*Sariq devni minib*» captivate readers with their adventurous plots and profound messages. *Harry Potter* teaches that every hardship brings relief and that life is a blend of light and dark. It also explores the idea that sometimes strangers can care for us more than family, showing children that love and kindness can come from unexpected places. Meanwhile, «*Sariq devni minib*» conveys the value of honesty, showing that achieving anything in life requires hard work and determination.

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